

PROFESSIONALS' REPRESENTATION OF COMMUNICATION DISORDERS

Social Representation

¹Akhila Rahul,²Jim Saroj Winston

¹Speech Language Pathologist, ²Junior Research Fellow

¹Department of Speech-Language Pathology,

¹JSS Institute of Speech and Hearing, Mysuru, India

Abstract: The present study probed into the level of knowledge that professionals have regarding the causes and characteristics of communication disorders and how the terminology 'communication disorders' is represented. A cross-sectional survey design was employed wherein 192 professionals between 20-55 years of age, belonging to various professional disciplines participated voluntarily. The participants filled an online survey consisting of multiple-choice based questions and a free association task. The findings indicate that individuals from most professional sectors were not aware of 'communication disorders' and failed to recognize the detrimental factors contributing to communication disorders. The present study's findings are conclusive that there is a lack of knowledge and awareness about communication disorders among various professional disciplines. Massive structured awareness campaigns are required to reach the masses.

IndexTerms - Awareness, social representation, professionals, communication disorders, early identification.

I. INTRODUCTION

Communication is the process by which partners exchange ideas, thoughts, and feelings through verbal or non-verbal modalities. The term 'communication disorders' encompasses a wide array of disorders affecting a person's ability to comprehend language and produce linguistic units to express him/ herself (American Speech-Language-Hearing Association, 1988; Ruscello, St. Louis, & Mason, 1991). A communication disorder can be congenital or acquired and can occur as a primary condition or can exist due to any other disorder or medical condition affecting the nervous system, auditory system, or speech subsystems (American Speech-Language-Hearing Association, 1988). Consequently, a communication disorder may affect a person's societal and emotional well-being and result in cognitive and behavioral difficulties (Lewis, Freebairn, & Taylor, 2000).

It has been reported that there is a relatively higher prevalence of communication disorders in India. According to the Census of India (2011), the prevalence of various communication disorders in India is around 30% relative to the total population. It was also reported by Konadath et al., 2013, that 6.07% of the rural population in India is at risk for communication disorders. Also, there is a greater prevalence reported for hearing-related disorders than speech and language disorders. These equivocal reports could be because a significant section of the Indian society is unaware of communication disorders. Several studies have probed the awareness of communication disorders among the general public across the Indian subcontinent. Rao, Sharmila, and Rishita (2002) studied the public's awareness and attitudes in Andhra Pradesh and reported that literacy is an essential factor in determining awareness and that awareness about communication disorders was less among illiterates. Shanbal and Arunraj (2016) indicated that the lack of awareness and knowledge about a communication disorder might result in false beliefs and hopes and delay early identification and intervention of communication disorders.

It is necessary to understand what the target population think regarding a particular phenomenon of interest to design and execute effective awareness programs. The current study attempts to explore how the concept of communication disorders is represented among the professionals. For the purpose of the present study, professionals have been defined as an individual with minimum of graduation degree and working in primary sectors like medical, paramedical, engineering, education, finance and business. Social representation has been discussed over several decades and has been applied in research on several human behaviors. It is considered as a collection of ideas, beliefs, and practices that enables individuals to orient themselves in society (Bimpitso & Petridou, 2012). The theory of social representation (SRT) has its origin in the 1960s, and Moscovici, a French social psychologist, coined the term 'social representation'. According to Moscovici, SRT affirms that each individual is influenced by the environment that he/ she belongs to, and the environment would shape their reactions and thoughts. Social representations (SR) are of knowledge, concepts, values, and images that individuals create regarding a phenomenon (Höjjer, 2011). It can also be considered as the practical thinking that underlies a phenomenon (Moscovici, 2000). Social representations revolve around two concepts; anchoring and objectifying. When we encounter a concept or phenomenon, we initially tend to anchor it through an active thought process that would link the new concept with our experience and memory (Alexandri, Papailiou, & Nikolaou, 2017; Höjjer, 2011). Secondly, we transfer the meaning associated with the new concept by linking with our memory and experience to something pre-existing in our lives (Höjjer, 2011). Thus, studying the social representation of a concept or idea among a given population or society would enable the understanding of knowledge and perceptions of individuals in the population/ society (Jovchelovitch, 2019). A plethora of studies have implemented SRT to study the perceptions of different classes in the society (Keczer, File, Orosz, & Zimbardo, 2016; Linton, Germundsson, Heimann, & Danermark, 2015). The focus on the knowledge of individuals and how a population/ society believes and behaves makes SRT the best research methodology to explore the perceptions of diverse professionals on communication disorders (Keczer et al., 2016).

Thus, the present study aimed at exploring professionals' social representation of communication disorders. The present study's specific objectives were to probe into the awareness of communication disorders, causes, characteristics, and multidisciplinary approaches to treatment among the various professional sections and understand how the concept of 'communication disorders' is represented in the professional community. The study would also throw light into the application of the social representation methods in the field of communication disorders.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The ethical clearance was obtained from the parent institute's Ethical Committee before the commencement of the research.

2.1 Study Design

The study was carried out using a cross-sectional survey design, and professionals belonging to various disciplines were recruited through snowball sampling method. The data was collected using the Google forms platform, and the link to the questionnaire was forwarded by the researchers to acquaintances personally and through social media and further forwarded to multiple other individuals.

2.2 Selection and Description of Participants

A total of 196 graduate professionals in the age range of 20 to 55 years participated in the study. The data obtained from four participants were eliminated as they were incomplete (n=192). The participants were then grouped according to their professional sectors comprising medical, engineering, paramedical, education, finance, and business. The demographic details of the participants are given in Figure 2.1 (a and b).

Fig. 2.1 (a). Demographic details: Age of participants

Fig. 2.1 (b). Demographic details: Professional sector of participants

2.2 Material and Data Collection

Each participant filled a questionnaire comprising of three sections. The first section of the questionnaire included demographic details of the participants. The second section comprised five multiple-choice questions that focused on probing into the risk factors of communication disorders and early identification and management. The final section constituted a free association task, which required the participants to describe five words/ phrases that come to their minds when they hear the term 'communication disorder.' The task was employed to understand how the concept is represented in the professionals' minds and to understand the semantic content of the response (Keczer et al., 2016). Over the years, the task has been used to elicit free associations relating to a stimulus concept to understand social representation (Abric, 2003). The responses of social representation would reveal central segments around which the concept is represented generally in the population and several peripheral segments that are variable in the population. The second open-ended question recognized the awareness and role of multidisciplinary management (Keczer et al., 2016). The questionnaire was validated for content by five experienced speech-language pathologists.

2.3 Analysis and Statistics

The questionnaire responses were subjected to descriptive statistical analyses to understand the relative proportion of professionals who are aware of communication disorders and understand their level of knowledge. Further, the chi-square test (Statistical Package for Social Sciences; version 20.0) was employed to explore any association between the responses and the professional disciplines.

The free association task responses were subjected to categorization by the three researchers and involved condensing individual responses into groups based on the semantic content. The data upon categorization fell into 14 categories and is represented graphically in a maximum tree. They were further analyzed for co-occurrence through Iramuteq software, an R-interface for multidimensional analysis of texts and surveys (Ratinaud, 2009). The graphical representation, called the 'maximum tree,' given by Flament (1981), displays the response categories as nodes/ circles and connections/ linkages between the nodes. The node's size indicates the frequency of the response categories from the population, and the connections denote the co-occurrence of responses. Further, the size of the linkages between any two nodes indicates the frequency of professionals who have reported both the responses (Flament, 1981).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 192 professionals participated in the present study, of which 55% (n=107) were males, and 45% (n=85) were females. 52% (n=100) indicated that their place of origin was urban. The data was further subjected to descriptive analysis to compute the knowledge and awareness of communication disorders quantitatively.

3.1 Knowledge about communication disorders

The majority of the participants (n=128) reported that genetic/ congenital is the cause of communication disorders. The results are further specifically tabulated in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1. Frequency of responses for causes of communication disorders among professionals

Causes	Percentage
Genetic /congenital	25
Family history	14
Consanguinity	4
Maternal alcohol/ smoking	6
Maternal infection	4
X-ray radiation/ Chemical exposure	4
Late pregnancy	3
Early pregnancy	2
Complications during delivery	5
Delayed birth cry	4
High fever/chickenpox/ other infections	3
Fits/ seizures	6
Accidents / falls	11
Aging	9

The second section consisted of a questionnaire that focused on whether communication disorders are curable, the risk factors, and the professionals involved and responsible for assessment and intervention. A final question tapped the participants' opinion about what they would do if they find a child at risk/ suspecting of communication disorder. The descriptive analysis of the responses for the section revealed that 93% of the professionals have the presumption that communication disorders are curable. The percentages of responses of the professional sectors about the population at risk for communication disorders are given in Tables 3.2.

Table 3.2: Percentage of responses of professional sectors on the population at risk for communication disorders

Percentage	Medical	Paramedical	Engineering	Business	Finance	Education
All Equally	27.5	42.5	46.5	46	53.8	48
Majorly Ped.	50	47.5	30.3	38.5	30.7	32
Majorly Ger.	12.2	2.5	2.3	0	0	4
Majorly Adu.	10.3	7.5	20.9	15.5	15.5	16

It was also found that a more significant number of professionals would seek medical consultation if a child is delayed in acquiring developmental speech and language milestones. Around 54% (n=104) of the professionals indicated that they would consult medical professionals and 33% (n=64) of the participants reported that they would consult audiologist/ speech-language pathologists. It is noteworthy that the professionals also reported that they would wait (7%, n=14) or undertake other measures such as considering religious beliefs or rituals (6%, n=11). Further, it was interesting to explore any association between the professionals' responses and their field of expertise. Chi-square test was carried out, and the results revealed that there was no significant association between the professional sector and the responses of the professionals ($\chi^2(7, N=192) = 25.18, p > 0.05$).

3.2 Representation of communication disorders

The response from the free association task was analyzed for content and then categorized manually into 14 categories. The frequencies of occurrence of the categories of responses are given in Fig. 3.1 below. The most frequently occurring response category was found to be "not aware."

Fig. 3.1. Frequency of occurrence of the different response categories

Further, the categories were subjected to co-occurrence analysis, and the results are represented graphically in a 'maximum tree.' The co-occurrence analysis presents two primary nodes (Fig.3.2) 'not aware' and 'speech and language deficit.' The category 'not aware' was linked to 'internet search engine,' and the category 'speech and language deficit' was linked to communication problems, comprehension deficits, socialization, fluency, sound, and voice. It is evident from the maximum tree that the most robust links appeared between the categories: speech and language deficit and hearing impairment (15) and speech and language deficit and fluency (9). The number in parentheses indicates the number of common ties present between the two linked categories indicating the frequency of professionals who have reported both the response categories.

Fig. 3.2. Maximum tree representation of the representation of communication disorders among professionals

IV. DISCUSSION

The current study reports the knowledge and awareness of communication disorders among various professional sectors and the representation of communication disorders in professionals' minds.

The results of the present study highlight the lack of awareness among various professional sectors. It was reported from a recent study conducted in Karnataka state (India) by Shanbal and Arunraj (2016) that there is a need for increased public awareness campaigns and orientation programs so that all sections of the society are aware of the different communication disorders and the implications in the lives of individuals with disability. It is evident from the results of the present study that the various professional sectors lack knowledge about communication disorders and also that the concept of communication disorders is under-represented in the community. This is perceptible from the co-occurrence analysis of the response categories which reveals that 'not aware' was the prominent response category, indicating that most of the professionals have preliminary information and knowledge regarding individuals with communication disorders in society. The node "not aware" was linked to 'internet search engine' which indicates that a small section of the participants used the search engine to respond to the questionnaire. The other prominent response nodes were speech and language deficits connected to communication problems, comprehension deficits, hearing impairment, fluency, socialization, voice, and sound. The results can thus be considered to be in conjunction with the findings of Shanbal and Arunraj (2016), who concluded that literacy was not a determining factor for deciding upon awareness of communication disorders among the public.

The results also indicated that the professionals believed medical management to be the primary intervention concerning communication disorders rather than the participation of SLP/ Audiologist. This puts in perspective the detrimental scenario in the society wherein many children are denied speech and language or audiological intervention at a young age due to a lack of awareness and knowledge among the professional groups. The professionals termed SLP/ Audiologist are under-represented in our society among the various sectors. This could have severe consequences and diminish the influence of factors such as the critical period, which holds the foundation for early identification and intervention of communication disorders (Lenneberg, 1967).

The social representation obtained in the study throws light on the actual behavior and not just the community's attitude, implying that there is a lack of awareness programs that need to be addressed on a war footing. This emphasizes that structured, widespread, and more effective awareness programs and campaigns must be conducted targeting the various sectors in the society individually. In the planning of such an awareness program, the findings of the present study will play a trivial role. The methodology adopted in the study proves efficient in understanding a community's beliefs and perceptions through the implementation of a free association task as this method of social representation proves to have a better interrelationship with the actual belief or behavior that is existent in society. The study portrays a comprehensive exemplar of implementing social representation studies in the research to understand a behavior existent in a given society (Marková, Moodie E & Plichotvá. 2000).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The study throws light on the perceptions of the various professionals on communication disorders. The present findings are conclusive that there is a need for structured campaigns targeting the educated sector of society. The different professional associations can collaborate with Governmental policies to reach the masses as rehabilitation professionals.

STRENGTH AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study has accomplished to obtain what exactly the professional sector assumes about communication disorders. However, the study needs to be taken to a higher level involving larger groups of professionals from diverse regions of the country. The study can also be taken forward, including principles of International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF) models (WHO, 2007).

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